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High-precision stabilization of copper rotary target motion for application in a laser-driven x-ray source

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X-ray sources based on laser-plasma interaction have a very promising range of applications due to their small source size and high fluence¹. To generate such x-rays, high-energy ultrashort laser pulses are tightly focused onto the surface of a target material, where they reach intensities greater than 10^{17} W/cm² and ionize the target material. At these intensities, the target material at the laser pulse impact position needs to be replenished prior to each subsequent laser pulse. Moreover, to achieve a high average power x-ray source, the repetition rate of the low-energy laser pulses (1mJ) needs to be high (1 kHz). Therefore, a situation is created where the target material needs to be very quickly replenished in-between subsequent laser pulses. As a solution, we use a fast-rotating copper target that provides fresh copper target material between laser pulses.

For this X-ray source to be useful, it is important that it be stable for long operation times. Therefore, the position of the target surface with respect to the laser focus needs to be very stable and well positioned within the Rayleigh length ($\sim 13\mu\text{m}$), as both the X-ray spectrum and fluence depend strongly on the pulse intensity at the target surface². This presents a complicated technical problem as factors such as the wobble in the rotational motion of the target and small curvatures in the target material are significant enough to exceed the Rayleigh length of the laser by at least an order of magnitude, and therefore move the target surface out of the focus.

In this paper we present a laser-driven x-ray source set-up at the Laser Laboratory for Acceleration and Applications (L2A2) at USC. The set-up uses a copper plate mounted on a motorized stage with 3 degrees of freedom (1 rotational and 2 linear). The stage both rotates continuously to replenish target material, while simultaneously correcting the position of the target surface so that it coincides with the focus of the laser. The correction is achieved by measuring a map of the target surface and then correcting for deviations along the focal axis with one of the linear stages. The stability of the focal correction has been verified using an optoNCDT 1320 sensor and has been shown to reduce the standard deviation of the target surface motion to $6.2\mu\text{m}$, which falls within the $13\mu\text{m}$ Rayleigh length of the laser pulse, ensuring the stability of the x-ray source.

The stabilization of this source will allow us to exploit its unique properties (ultrafast and small source size) for applications in phase contrast imaging, as well as to perform systematic studies about the physics of the laser plasma acceleration mechanism.

Figure 1: (Left) The variation in the target surface motion without correction (blue) and with correction (orange). The standard deviation of the uncorrected motion is $37.5\mu\text{m}$ whereas the standard deviation of the corrected motion is $6.2\mu\text{m}$. (Right) Target surface motion over a single rotation of the target. The timing of the applied focal correction is critical to stabilize the target motion. The dashed black lines show the standard deviation of the corrected motion about the mean position (solid line).

Figure 2: Picture of the copper target mounted on a rotary stage. The microscope objective is seen on the right side of the image. The high-intensity laser pulses emerge from the microscope objective and ionize the copper target material producing x-ray radiation.

¹ J. C. Kieffer, S. Fourmaux, and A. Krol; *In 19th International Conference and School on Quantum Electronics: Laser Physics and Applications*, **10226**, 1022612 (2017)

² L. Martín, J. Benlliure, D. Cortina-Gil, J. Penas, and C. Ruiz; *High Power Laser Science and Engineering*, **8** (2020).